

THE CONTENT AND FORMS OF SUPPORT FOR PROFESSIONAL SELF-DETERMINATION OF STUDENT TEACHERS

Reymbaeva Roza Saparbaevna,

PhD, Nukus branch of the Uzbek state university
of physical education and sport

Kaipnazarov Talgat Shamshetovich,

Ernazarova Raya Allanazarovna,

Patullaeva Aynura Sabitovna,

Nukus branch of the Uzbek state university
of physical education and sport assistant,
Nukus branch of the Uzbek state university
of physical education and sport

Abstract: Based on the author's concept of the semantic mechanisms of professional self-determination, the article reveals the content and forms of accompanying this process in the conditions of university teacher training.

The ways of integrating support into educational and extracurricular activities of students, in the process of internship are determined, the possibilities of modern information and communication technologies to support students' professional self-determination are shown. The requirements for the activity of a teacher-coach who supports the professional self-identification of student teachers are outlined.

Key words: pedagogical education, teacher training, professional self-determination, professional identity, teacher-coach, pedagogical support, individual educational trajectory.

The period of studentship is one of the key stages of entering the future profession, and the support of professional self-determination of students is a necessary component of the educational process.

At the same time, relatively few studies emphasize in the professional self-determination of a person its internal, individual-semantic component, the significance of experiencing an authentic professionally oriented experience and the formation of an identity as a condition for a meaningful choice and further self-development in a profession. It should also be noted that in the conditions of a post-industrial society and the individualization of education, the professional self-determination of students acquires a pronounced "existential", semantic character, assuming a qualitatively new level and content of the subjective activity of the individual in the vocational field.

The purpose of this article is to substantiate the content and forms of professional self-determination of student teachers on the basis of the author's concept of semantic mechanisms of professional self-determination. The development of the content and specific forms of support for the professional self-determination of students requires an understanding of what psychological and pedagogical mechanisms will be involved in this process. The category of meaning in the context of the problems of personal and professional self-determination was updated in the classic works of M.R.Ginzburg, E.A. Klimov, D.A.Leontiev. In modern conditions, the semantic aspects of professional self-determination are of particular relevance. As noted by N.F.Rodichev, M.A.Sikorskaya-Dekanova, I.S.Sergeev,, the post-industrial type of professional self-determination is characterized by the fact that "the content of professional self-determination becomes a system of meanings that act as the internal driving force of a person in his professional activity". Under the conditions of individualization of higher education, the meaning-forming characteristics of individual educational trajectories are associated with the need for meaningful choices and the design by students of a personal educational route.

In foreign studies, the semantic mechanisms of professional self-determination are studied within the framework of a phenomenological approach that emphasizes the role of self-understanding of professional development and the formation of identity in a profession through narrative and discursive practices . The leading new formations

of professional development and self-determination are the image of "I am a professional", the experience of authentic experience of professional activity, the integrity of self-perception of the way of becoming in the profession. This approach has found application in teacher professional development support programs in countries such as the USA, Australia, China (Hong Kong), Great Britain, Latvia, Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands when studying the professional development of a teacher at its various stages and covers such categories as students of specialized colleges, pedagogical universities and universities, interns, young teachers, teachers with experience. An analysis of the programs we analyzed allows us to identify significant factors in the formation of a teacher's professional identity:

experience of independent pedagogical activity, self-efficacy, reflective attitude to professional growth, support of the pedagogical community, dialogical environment, awareness of modern innovative developments and development trends in the field of education, knowledge of the objective requirements for pedagogical activity. At the same time, the ideas and approaches listed above require the development of ways to integrate them into the educational process of higher education, and this article presents the results of such a study.

To determine the content and forms of supporting the professional self-determination of student teachers, the author's concept of semantic mechanisms and the model of supporting the professional self-determination of students-future teachers were used. We relied on the idea that the leading semantic mechanisms of students' professional self-determination are the design of a professional future and reflective comprehension of the experience gained during the implementation of the project of their professional self-development. Support should ensure the implementation of a holistic cycle of the process of generating the personal meaning of the profession through interrelated types of activity: designing a professional future, implementing the project in real activity and reflective comprehension of the experience gained. The purpose of support is to create conditions for the formation of students as meaningful

subjects of the professional path through the development of cultural practices for constructing professional identity, which are implemented through narrative and discursive methods. The stages of support include sense-orientation, the essence of which is to master the value-semantic foundations of pedagogical activity, sense-setting, which is realized through the design of the process of professional self-development, the organizational and activity stage, at which the planning of ways to implement one's project in real activity, the activity stage, providing immersion in a quasi-professional and professional contexts and the acquisition of experience in solving pedagogical problems, the stage of reflection, at which the mastered experience becomes the subject of comprehension, thanks to which it is "embedded" in the emerging professional identity of students. The formation of the professional identity of student teachers was considered as the main result of support and the leading criterion of professional self-determination .

The model we proposed to support the professional self-determination of student teachers was tested in the course of experimental work, which was carried out during January-October 2019 on the basis of the Karakalpak State University.

university. The study involved junior bachelors, undergraduates in pedagogy and teachers of the Department of Psychology and Pedagogy. Maintenance stages, their content and methodological support, forms of implementation, expected results and ways to support the maintenance process using modern information and communication technologies.

In the course of approbation of the model of supporting the professional self-determination of student teachers, the requirements for the activities of the teacher organizing this process were identified. The teacher is expected to be dialogic in communication, the lack of formalized pedagogical interaction, an individual approach, trust in communication, and a focus on productive collaboration.

The leading tasks of the teacher are determined: motivating students for professional self-development and facilitation of this process, readiness to build

"supportive relationships". It has also been established that the specifics of supporting professional self-determination as a semantic process requires additional competencies from the teacher. These include the ability to act as a consultant not only on professional and pedagogical problems, but also in case of difficulties associated with personal and professional growth, as well as to act as a project management specialist, which allows organizing student identification activity. In this regard, we considered it necessary to introduce the term "teacher coach" in order to emphasize the features of the teacher's activity in the proposed variant of support.

As the study showed, interrelated stages of support can be implemented in the process of university teacher training, integrated into it through educational and extracurricular forms, a system of practices, provided that they are enriched with meaning-forming methods and ensure the design-practice-reflection cycle. We also note that the use of narrative and reflective techniques in working with students requires the development of appropriate competencies in them.

In the course of experimental work, the possibilities of modern information and communication technologies (blogging, storytelling, etc.) were identified to stimulate the formation of meaning and support the process of professional self-identification of students, which is ensured by their dialogism, conditions for unfolding narrative activity and professional pedagogical discourse, stimulating directed reflection pedagogical experience, operational feedback and psychological support.

A necessary element of the proposed support option is monitoring, developed in accordance with the initial theoretical positions and aimed at tracking changes in the formation of the main components of professional self-determination of student teachers¹. The diagnostic complex includes methods that allow assessing the dynamics of professional identity (A. A. Ozerina's questionnaire), the level of professional self-esteem (the author's version of the semantic differential), changes in descriptors that reflect the implementation of the semantic mechanisms of professional self-

determination, identified on the basis of content analysis of the essays "My professional future".

Based on the concept of semantic mechanisms, the content and optimal forms of supporting professional self-determination are determined, which organically fit into the process of university teacher training. The semantic foundations of professional self-determination of students are emphasized, which provide a meaningful choice of the trajectory of the professional path. In connection with the special content of accompaniment, the conditions required for the implementation of the mechanisms of meaning formation embedded in it are characterized. We assign a key role to the teacher-coach, who performs several interrelated functions in interaction with students.

The results of the study will be useful in the conditions of individualization of education for the development of students' ability to design their professional path, translate their project into reality and comprehend new experience, which contributes to the formation of their professional identity. The listed existential competencies are universal and will ensure self-determination of development not only during the period of university education, but also at subsequent stages of personal and professional development.

Referneces:

1. Belyakova E. G. The problem of modeling the process of forming the professional identity of students - future teachers from the standpoint of the value-semantic approach // *Pedagogical Education in Russia*. - 2018. - No 5. - P.68–73.
2. Belyakova E. G. Accompaniment of professional self-determination of students - future teachers: value-semantic approach // *Innovative projects and programs in education*. - 2018. - No 4 (58). —S.64–72.
3. Zeer E.F., Zavodchikov D.P., Zinnatova M.V., Lebedeva E.V. Individual educational trajectory as a setting of the subject in the system of continuous education // *Scientific dialogue*. - 2017. - No 1. - P. 266–279.

4. Povarenkov Yu. P. Psychological structure of the subject of the professional path // *Bulletin of the Vyatka State University for the Humanities*. - 2008. - T. 1. - No 2. - P. 9–16.
5. Sergeev I. S., Rodichev N. F., Sikorskaya-Dekanova M. A. Professional self-determination and its support in the post-industrial world: an attempt to forecast // *Professional education and labor market*. - 2018. - No 4. - P.39–50.
6. Amott P. Identification — a process of self-knowing realized within narrative practices for teacher educators during times of transition // *Professional Development in Education*. - 2018. - Vol. 44.-No4. —P. 476–491.
7. Izadinia M. A review of research on student teachers' professional identity // *British Educational Research Journal*. - 2013. - Vol. 39. - No 4. - Pr. 694–713.
8. Kelchtermans G. Who I am in how I teach is the message: Self-understanding, vulnerability and reflection // *Teachers and Teaching*. - 2009. - No 15. - P. 257–272.